

Project	Website	Objectives/key words	Lead/coordinator	Location and Sites	Ecosystem types	Restoration approaches studied (e.g., Habitat improvement, protection, seeding, predator removal)
3D-PARE	https://www.giteco.unican.es/proyectos/3dpare/index.html	3D printing artificial reefs, aiming to test the materials used in the eco-friendly concrete; Habitat enhancement, biodiversity increase, blue/green infrastructure, hybrid coastal infrastructure, 3D printed reefs, multifunctional structures	Construction Technology Applied Research Group (GITECO) of the University of Cantabria; XXXXX	UK (Poole Bay), France (Saint-Malo Bay), Spain (Santander Bay), Portugal (Matosinhos Harbour)	Harbours/bays Marine, coastal habitats (artificial reefs, subtidal and intertidal zones)	Habitat improvement, biodiversity enhancement, bio-receptive concrete, creation of artificial reefs
A-AAGORA - Overall	https://a-aagora.eu/	Transformative innovations, quadruple-helix approach. Developing a blueprint for an Atlantic-Arctic agora. scaling up solutions, demonstrations	University of Aveiro (XXXXX)	Norway (Troms), Ireland (County Cork), Portugal (Centro Region)	coastal and marine ecosystems vulnerable to climate change, particularly areas susceptible to sea-level rise and biodiversity loss (https://oceanandsociety.org/en/projects/blueprint-for-atlantic-arctic-agora ; https://allatlanticocean.org/all-atlantic-projects/a-aagora/)	project utilizes ecosystem-based management and NbS, including blue reforestation, to reduce pressures on ecosystems, increase resilience, and mitigate climate impacts (https://allatlanticocean.org/all-atlantic-projects/a-aagora/)
A-AAGORA - Demo Site 1 (Norway)	https://a-aagora.eu/	Biodiversity restoration; EBM inside and outside MPAs; Ecotourism development	UiT/Karlsøy kommune	Norway	Kelp forest	protection of remaining kelp forests; removal of sea urchins and rebuilding of natural predatory wolf fish stocks; mapping of biodiversity hotspots and citizen involvement to enhance ecosystem-based management (EBM)
A-AAGORA - Demo Site 2 (Ireland)	https://a-aagora.eu/	Supporting decision-making for coastal erosion through science and community engagement; volunteer-led activities for wetland restoration	UCC/Cork County Council	Ireland	Beach; Dunes; saltmarsh/wetland	Monitoring beach/dune relationships; bottom-up social innovation; increase of the local biodiversity and interest in local communities

A-AAGORA - Demo Site 3 (Portugal)	https://a-aagora.eu/	Reduction of Marine Litter; Resilience to coastal erosion; Climate Change Mitigation	University of Aveiro/CCDR	Portugal	Beach; Dunes; seagrass; saltmarsh/wetland	Integrate and leverage existing marine litter related activities; produce ocean literacy materials; real-time services; bridging sand beach monitoring and sand dunes, for an integrated coastal alert system; bridging blue carbon and ports decarbonization blue carbon sequestration abatement of GHG emissions; reduction of GHG emissions
CLIMAREST - Overall	https://climarest.eu/	Demonstration and upscaling of restoration solutions, making solutions available for future projects. Development of a holistic restoration toolbox.	SINTEF	Norway, Ireland, Portugal, France, Spain	Arctic fjords, Seagrass meadows, Oyster reefs, Sedimentary soft-bed ecosystems, Rocky substrates	N/A
CLIMAREST - DEMO Site 1 (Svalbard)	https://climarest.eu/	Protect and restore the integrity of the benthic ecosystem in an arctic fjord (<i>passive restoration</i>) & <i>Design and construct a hybrid blue-grey nature-based solution to address coastal erosion in Longyearbyen (eco-engineering)</i>	SINTEF, NINA, NTU	Norway (Svalbard)	Arctic fjords	Wastewater treatment & hybrid blue-grey nature-based construction (eco-engineering)
CLIMAREST - DEMO Site 2 (Ireland)	https://climarest.eu/	Test transplantation of seagrass species	University of Galloway, University of Malaga	Ireland	Seagrass meadows	Transplantation & seeding
CLIMAREST - DEMO Site 3 (France)	https://climarest.eu/	Facilitate the restoration of the native oyster <i>Ostrea edulis</i> & assess the effectiveness of ecological engineering on marine artificial structures	Seabio, Ifremer	France	Oyster reefs	Design and deployment of native oyster larvae settlement structures
CLIMAREST - DEMO Site 4 (Spain)	https://climarest.eu/	Mitigate the environmental impacts of mussel farming on soft bottom benthic communities & mitigate the impact of intensive fishing on a key species (lobster)	University of Vigo, University of Alicante	Spain	Sedimentary soft-bed ecosystems	Deployment of concrete ecological reefs under mussel farms & reintroduction of european lobster
CLIMAREST - DEMO Site 5 (Madeira)	https://climarest.eu/	Restore urchin barrens into macroalgae dominated biotopes through active "reforestation"	ARDITI	Madeira	Rocky substrate	Restore urchin barrens into macroalgae dominated biotopes through active "reforestation"
REST-COAST	https://rest-coast.eu/	Improve coastal management through a holistic river-to-sea approach: develop financial arrangements, governance frameworks, plans for coastal adaptation, new tools for risk reduction, restoration best practice, support the Green Deal	Maritime Engineering Laboratory in the Catalonia University of Technology UPC-BarcelonaTech	Wadden Sea, Ebro Delta, Venice Lagoon, Vistula Lagoon, Foros Bay, Rhone Delta, Sicily Lagoon, Arcachon Bay, Nahal Dalia	Coastal ecosystems	Restoration of coastal biodiversity and ecosystem services: Saltmarshes restoration, seagrass transplantation, sand nourishment, etc.

RESTORESEAS	https://www.restoreseas.net/#:~:text=RESTORESEAS%20aim%20to%20improve%20resilience	habitat suitability/biodiversity models for the Atlantic Ocean, conducting surveys/mapping, comparatively testing different approaches (clonal versus sexual propagation) for restoration of different types of marine habitats, Developing efficient strategies (eDNA of seawater and sediments) for long-term monitoring of the benefits of restoration and conservation	Biogeographical Ecology and Evolution, Centre of Marine Sciences (CCMAR)	Around Atlantic Ocean, Eastern South America and West Africa (--> interesting as, West-Africa reportedly often overlooked (cf. BMAA D1.3 report, page 34)).	Coral, seagrass, seaweed	N/A
Thames21	https://www.thames21.org.uk/	Coordinating voluntary river clean ups, citizen science initiatives, monitoring of river quality and pollution in Thames catchment/ focus on nature based solutions to issues facing rivers in the Thames basin	N/A (Thames21 is an independent charity, it is not a project and does not have a lead partner as such)	London, UK	River, river catchment	N/A

N/A N/A N/A N/A N/A N/A N/A
 N/A N/A N/A Note: "XXXXX" used to avoid sharing personal information. N/A N/A N/A

The information is saved in a separate file.

Restoration successes (Yes/No)	What indices, if any, were used to gauge restoration success (e.g. Survival, Areal increase, biodiversity indices, invasive species, carbon sequestration)	What social metrics, if any, were used to gauge success?
<p>Yes, increases in biodiversity were observed after 6 months in all countries. After 2.5 years, over 118 species were recorded.</p> <p>(https://www.bournemouth.ac.uk/research/projects/3dpare-3d-printing-artificial-reefs-atlantic https://staffprofiles.bmth.ac.uk/display/poster/337603)</p>	<p>The study did not specifically focus on restoration, but it included measurements of species diversity and community composition, both on the reef unit itself and in its associated ecosystem.</p>	<p>Not explicitly mentioned, but community engagement is implied; citizen science not explicitly stated (https://itrs2023.org/2022/09/08/3d-printed-artificial-reef-deployment-in-the-atlantic-coast-project-overview-monitoring-and-results/); https://staffprofiles.bmth.ac.uk/display/poster/337603)</p>
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<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Community engagement (e.g. in protection of wolffish)</p>
<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Community engagement</p>

N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A
Evaluation on going	Biodiversity indices, litter quantities, contaminants concentrations	Citizen awareness
Evaluation on going	Survival rates, Genetic biodiversity indexes	N/A
Evaluation on going	Biodiversity indexes, carbon sequestration, survival rates, water quality	N/A
Evaluation on going	Respiration rates, biodiversity indexes, biomass, lobster trajectories	N/A
Evaluation on going	Biodiversity indexes, population densities.	none
N/A, on going	A database was setup on the measuring of the status of restorations, in terms of biophysical, ESS and biodiversity indicators. A scoring system was setup using EUNIS biotope mapping and correlated ESS production to assess the impact of climate change, SLR and restoration measures	A whole WP (lead by IUCN) is dedicated to governance and social domains related implementation barriers and developing and testing enabling indicators

N/A	"In terms of how the project determines success, this is mainly done through the evaluation of metrics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as deliverables completed, number of stakeholders engaged in the project, and number of events held under the project. Another more qualitative measure of success on the project is the level and depth of collaboration between partners and between different countries involved in the project, linking to the added value of RESTORESEAS." (BMAA D1.3 report)	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A

What long-term monitoring, if any, is/was applied to monitor success (both physical, ecological and community monitoring)?

2 years of SCUBA and BRUV/RUV surveys were undertaken with four survey campaigns per year between March and October

Yes, long-term monitoring included SCUBA surveys, photogrammetry, and BRUV surveys to assess species richness and ecosystem functionality. (<https://staffprofiles.bmth.ac.uk/display/poster/337603>;
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Alice-Hall-6/publication/328095684_Artificial_reef_3D_printing_for_Atlantic_Area_3DPARE/links/5bb72d3da6fcc9552d43f90/Artificial-reef-3D-printing-for-Atlantic-Area-3DPARE.pdf)

ecological assessments and community-based monitoring (regarding NbS and EBM strategies) (<https://a-aagora.eu/overview/>; <https://allatlanticocean.org/all-atlantic-projects/a-aagora/>)

Community engagement (e.g. in protection of wolffish)

Community engagement

N/A
N/A
ecological monitoring (field campaigns)
4 and 1 month, 2 years is planned
ecological monitoring (field campaigns)
2 years, monthly, of scuba diving and ROV
benthic communities with special emphasis in algae cover, algae diversity and urchin densities. Also integrating frequency and occurrences of 24 indicator taxa through DiveReporter
In many cases the long term monitoring of restorations is an issue that needs to be resolved as part of implementation planning. In some cases it is part of already existing long term biophysical and social monitoring programs of regional governments and research institutes.

N/A

N/A

N/A

N/A

Was there community participation, citizen science in your case studies?	Did you have any regulatory challenges/successes?
Indirect mention of community engagement, no direct references to citizen science (https://itrs2023.org/2022/09/08/3d-printed-artificial-reef-deployment-in-the-atlantic-coast-project-overview-monitoring-and-results/ ; https://www.bournemouth.ac.uk/research/projects/3dpare-3d-printing-artificial-reefs-atlantic)	Marine Management Organisation provided an exception for a licence on scientific grounds, otherwise this would have been a major challenge; The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial success.
Yes, community participation, including local stakeholders in the planning and implementation of restoration activities --> participatory approach (https://a-aagora.eu/overview/ ; https://oceanandsociety.org/en/projects/blueprint-for-atlantic-arctic-agera)	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
Yes	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
Yes	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.

N/A	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
N/A	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
Yes	
Volunteers (mainly university students), Scuba diving centres (ACMARAL network), Environmental protection agencies (Ireland and Andalusia), fishermen (FENAPA - association of traditional fishermen from Caleta de Vélez, Málaga), Scuba divers, Environmental NGOs (Cost Watch Ireland), Environmental associations (Equilibrio Marino)	In Malaga we had issues to get licensing
N/A	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
Yes, students of Aquaculture and Marine Sciences, Divers	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.
yes	yes, permits for deployment of artificial reef structures
Yes, at pilot site level: development of platforms to bring together various local actors from business to governance, also associations for environmental conservation (meeting twice/year on average)	The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success. In the NL case, a large upscaling program, beyond the present demonstrations is being funded based on three pillars: Ecology, Economy and Safety. Funding magnitude is approx. 300 million euros. REST-COAST is supporting this upscaling program with science and process.

<p>Yes, including citizen science and fishers and volunteers (the volunteers helping with the coral feeding and placing them in their natural habitat once strong enough), cf. BMAA D1.3 report.; "The fishers become actively engaged in restoration activities, and the scientists benefit from having access to the fishers' ships, which saves financial and logistical costs in their species distribution mapping activities." (BMAA D1.3 report, page 35); Involvement in organising the "Marine Forest Festival" (opportunity for citizens/the public to learn about coral restoration work, directly involving involved fishers)</p>	<p>The fact to be publicly funded can be seen as (initial) success.</p>
<p>N/A</p>	<p>Availability of public funding to be checked.</p>
<p>N/A N/A</p>	<p>N/A N/A</p>

No of scientific papers on restoration approaches published
3 so far, 2 more planned
N/A
N/A
2

N/A
aggregated: 2 published, 2 to come in the coming months
Not in this project
2, another 2 to be submitted in the next months
N/A
1
8 papers relevant to advance methods for monitoring (e.g. Passive Acoustic Monitoring, Remote Video Foraging System), assess grazing pressure, Crowdsourcing monitoring with Dive Reporter and report new species occurrence See REST-COAST website for progress on outputs of publications as it is a work in progress

N/A

N/A

N/A
N/A

Number of policy reports published	No of science-policy presentations given	No of scientific presentations given	Any resulting private/public investment resulting from project restoration activities	Website and other social media viewing metrics	Project partners	Schedule (Planned project start and end day/month/year)
Information not found	Information not found	Information not found	Information not found	Information not found	https://www.giteco.unican.es/proyectos/3dpare/partners.html Universidad de Cantabria; University of Porto; ESITC CAEN; IPMA; Bournemouth University	Start: Spring/Summer 2020 (to be confirmed)
N/A	A-AAGORA participates in scientific and policy-focused events; specific counts on presentations is not available, but the project's active engagement with stakeholders and policymakers indicates regular contributions to science-policy dialogues	Exact numbers unavailable, but A-AAGORA's consortium is involved in academic and scientific forums, presenting findings and methods on restoration and climate resilience	N/A	615 LinkedIn followers (data on 27 October 2024)	https://a-aagora.eu/partners/	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	https://a-aagora.eu/partners/	N/A
N/A	N/A	4	N/A	CLIMAREST website	https://a-aagora.eu/partners/	N/A

N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	https://a-aagora.eu/partners/	N/A
List on website empty --> seeminly none yet	N/A	N/A	N/A	1066 LinkedIn followers (data on 27 October 2024)	https://climarest.eu/partners/	N/A
List on website empty --> seeminly none yet	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	https://climarest.eu/partners/	
0	0	1 talk and 3 posters	Collaborations with scuba diving centres and filming	N/A	https://climarest.eu/partners/	
List on website empty --> seeminly none yet	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	https://climarest.eu/partners/	
List on website empty --> seeminly none yet		0	6	0	https://climarest.eu/partners/	
List on website empty --> seeminly none yet	3 (IFCN, DRM and Maritime authority)		7 No		https://climarest.eu/partners/	
One	One plus one with clustered projects (next December)	N/A	Identification of potential for scalability of pilote sites has begun; too early to define the best plan yet (BMAA D1.3 report, page 33)	600 LinkedIn followers (data on 27 October 2024)	https://rest-coast.eu/partners/	1/11/2022-30/04/2026

N/A	N/A	N/A	airports of portugal ANA (seagrass), cement company SECIL (seagrass), Foundation Belmiro de Azevedo (corals), Municipality of Cascais (kelp)	www.restoreseas.net	https://www.restoreseas.net/project-partners/	2022-2025
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	3228 LinkedIn followers (data on 27 October 2024)	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Status	Funding	Type of project	Comments
Completed	Interreg	Research/IA	N/A
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Innovation Action	Classification of CLIMAREST and A-AAGORA to be checked and confirmed whether correct: Innovation Action
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Innovation Action	N/A
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Innovation Action	N/A

Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Innovation Action	N/A
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Research and Innovation Action (to be confirmed)	N/A
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Research and Innovation Action (to be confirmed)	
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Research and Innovation Action (to be confirmed)	
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Research and Innovation Action (to be confirmed)	
ONgoing	Horizon Europe	Research and Innovation Action (to be confirmed)	
Ongoing	Horizon Europe	Research and Innovation Action (to be confirmed)	
Ongoing	Horizon	Research/IA	N/A

Ongoing	Biodiversa+	Research/IA	"A benefit for RESTORESEAS of being funded under Biodiversa+ is that the mid-term report meetings have previously been held in person and have included other projects under the same fund, fostering a space for informal networking discussions with colleagues working on other projects in the same research area, a similar experience as was previously described by REST-COAST." (BMAA D1.3 report)
Ongoing	Diverse sources: https://www.thames21.org.uk/our-funders/	Charitable organisation	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A